

Supporting Information:

Forced Periodic Operation of Chemical Reactors: Origins of Performance Improvement Demonstrated on Methanol Synthesis

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Contents

1	Modeling $A \rightarrow C$	2
1.1	Continuous stirred tank reactor	2
1.2	Plug-flow tubular reactor	2
2	Modelling Methanol synthesis	3
2.1	Reactor Equation	3
2.2	Kinetics	4
2.2.1	Seidel kinetics	4
2.2.2	Kortuz kinetics	5
2.2.3	van Schagen kinetics	7
2.2.4	Nestler kinetics	7
2.2.5	Vanden Bussche kinetics	8
3	Optimization	9
3.1	Reaction $A \rightarrow C$	9
3.2	Methanol synthesis	10
4	Additional results	11
4.1	Suboptimal solution with FPO for $A \rightarrow C$	11
4.2	Methanol synthesis	13
4.2.1	Comparison: Isothermal and nonisothermal reactor with fixed temperature	13
4.2.2	Comparison: Isothermal and nonisothermal reactor with optimized temperature	15
4.2.3	Equilibrium	17
4.2.4	Linear reaction rate	19

1 Modeling A \rightarrow C

1.1 Continuous stirred tank reactor

The starting point is the component mole balance for species A, B, and C. The reaction rate is modeled using a power-law approach.

$$\frac{dn_A}{dt} = \dot{n}_{A, \text{in}}(t) - \dot{n}_A(t) - k n_A, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dn_B}{dt} = \dot{n}_{B, \text{in}}(t) - \dot{n}_B(t), \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dn_C}{dt} = -\dot{n}_C(t) + k n_A. \quad (3)$$

n_i is the mole number of component i , \dot{n}_i the molar flow rate, and k the reaction rate constant. Using the mole fraction y_i , we can express $n_i = n \cdot y_i$ and $\dot{n}_i = \dot{n} \cdot y_i$. Since $\dot{n}_{\text{in}} = \dot{n}_{\text{out}}$ (as the total mole number does not change due to the reaction), the final component balance for a CSTR becomes:

$$n \frac{dy_A}{dt} = \dot{n}_{\text{in}}(t) [y_{B, \text{in}}(t) - y_A] - k n y_A, \quad (4)$$

$$n \frac{dy_B}{dt} = \dot{n}_{\text{in}}(t) [y_{B, \text{in}}(t) - y_B], \quad (5)$$

$$n \frac{dy_C}{dt} = -\dot{n}_{\text{in}}(t) y_C + k n y_A. \quad (6)$$

1.2 Plug-flow tubular reactor

Starting again from the component mole balance, similar to the CSTR case, yields:

$$\frac{\partial n_A}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial w n_A}{\partial z} = -k n_A, \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial n_B}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial w n_B}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\partial n_C}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial w n_C}{\partial z} = k n_A, \quad (9)$$

ω is the flow velocity of the fluid and can be determined from the volumetric flow rate:

$$\omega = \frac{\dot{V}}{A} \quad (10)$$

The volumetric flow rate \dot{V} can be related to the molar flow rate using the ideal gas law:

$$\dot{V} = \frac{\dot{n}RT}{P} = \dot{n} \cdot \frac{V}{n} \quad (11)$$

Substituting into the expression for ω gives:

$$\omega = \frac{\dot{n} \cdot V}{n \cdot A} \quad (12)$$

For a cylindrical reactor, $V/A = l$, with l being the reactor length. This leads to:

$$\omega = \frac{\dot{n} \cdot l}{n} \quad (13)$$

Using this relation and applying the mole fraction definition as before, the resulting expression for the mole balance becomes:

$$n \frac{\partial y_A}{\partial t} + l \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \frac{\partial y_A}{\partial z} = -k n y_A, \quad (14)$$

$$n \frac{\partial y_B}{\partial t} + l \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \frac{\partial y_B}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (15)$$

$$n \frac{\partial y_C}{\partial t} + l \dot{n}_{\text{in}} \frac{\partial y_C}{\partial z} = k n y_A, \quad (16)$$

2 Modelling Methanol synthesis

2.1 Reactor Equation

As a starting point, the component material balance is used, considering both the gas phase and the solid phase.

$$\frac{\partial(n_i^G + n_i^S)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\omega n_i^G)}{\partial z} = m_{\text{cat}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \nu_{i,j} r_j, \quad (17)$$

Here, the flow velocity can also be expressed in terms of the molar flow rate.

$$\omega = \frac{\dot{n} \cdot l}{n} \quad (18)$$

By reformulating the velocity and applying the mole fraction definition as before, the following component molar balance is obtained [1].

$$n^G \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial t} + \dot{n} l \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial z} + m_{\text{cat}} q_{\text{sat}} P \left(\sum_{k=1}^{N_c} \frac{\partial \Theta_i}{\partial p_k} \frac{\partial y_k}{\partial t} - y_i \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \sum_{k=1}^{N_c} \frac{\partial \Theta_i}{\partial p_k} \frac{\partial y_k}{\partial t} \right) = m_{\text{cat}} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \nu_{i,j} r_j - y_i \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \nu_{i,j} r_j \right). \quad (19)$$

Due to the mole reducing character of the reaction, the molar flow rate \dot{n} is not constant. For this purpose the total molar balance is required.

$$\frac{\partial n^G}{\partial t} + l \frac{\partial \dot{n}}{\partial z} + m_{\text{cat}} q_{\text{sat}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \sum_{k=1}^{N_c} \frac{\partial \Theta_i}{\partial p_k} \frac{dp_k}{dt} = m_{\text{cat}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \nu_{i,j} r_j. \quad (20)$$

While the main paper focuses solely on the isothermal case, this Supporting Information also presents results for the non-isothermal operation. Consequently, an energy balance must be included [1].

$$\left(n^G c_p^G + m_{\text{cat}} c_{p,\text{cat}}^* \right) \frac{dT}{dt} + l \dot{n} c_p^G \frac{dT}{dz} + m_{\text{cat}} \sum_i \Delta H_{R,j} r_j + \alpha_{\text{cool}} A_{\text{wall}} (T - T_{\text{cool}}) + p m_{\text{cat}} q_{\text{sat}} \Delta H_{\text{ads}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \sum_{k=1}^{N_c} \frac{\partial \Theta_i}{\partial p_k} \frac{dy_k}{dt} = 0. \quad (21)$$

q_{sat} represents the relative amount of active surface centers and is related to the accumulation in the solid phase. Since this quantity is difficult to determine experimentally, and it was shown that its influence is minor [2], it is neglected in this work. This leads to the following simplified equations:

$$n^G \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial t} + \dot{n} l \frac{\partial y_i}{\partial z} = m_{\text{cat}} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \nu_{i,j} r_j - y_i \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \nu_{i,j} r_j \right) \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{\partial n^G}{\partial t} + l \frac{\partial \dot{n}}{\partial z} = m_{\text{cat}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_r} \nu_{i,j} r_j \quad (23)$$

$$\left(n^G c_p^G + m_{\text{cat}} c_{p,\text{cat}}^* \right) \frac{dT}{dt} + l \dot{n} c_p^G \frac{dT}{dz} = -m_{\text{cat}} \sum_i \Delta H_{R,j} r_j - \alpha_{\text{cool}} A_{\text{wall}} (T - T_{\text{cool}}) \quad (24)$$

These equations can be written in matrix-vector notation as

$$\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{x}) \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dt} + \mathbf{W}(\mathbf{x}) \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dz} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (25)$$

For a detailed definition of the individual matrices, the reader is referred to the appendix of [1].

2.2 Kinetics

Different kinetic models for methanol synthesis were used. All reactions rates contain the equilibrium constants $K_{p,CO}$, K_{p,CO_2} and $K_{p,rwgs}$ provided by Graaf and Winkelman (2016) [3].

2.2.1 Seidel kinetics

Reaction rates [4, 5]:

$$r_{CO} = (1 - \phi)k_1 \left(p_{CO}p_{H_2}^2 - \frac{p_{CH_3OH}}{K_{p,CO}} \right) \Theta^\ominus \Theta^4, \quad (26)$$

$$r_{CO_2} = \phi^2 k_2 \left(p_{CO_2}p_{H_2}^2 - \frac{p_{CH_3OH}p_{H_2O}}{K_{p,CO_2}p_{H_2}} \right) \Theta^{*2} \Theta^{\otimes 4}, \quad (27)$$

$$r_{rwgs} = \frac{\phi}{1 - \phi} k_3 \left(p_{CO_2} - \frac{p_{CO}p_{H_2O}}{K_{p,rwgs}p_{H_2}} \right) \Theta^* \Theta^\ominus. \quad (28)$$

with $p_i = p \cdot y_i$,

$$k_1 = \exp \left(\beta_1 - \beta_2 \left(\frac{523K}{T} - 1 \right) \right), \quad (29)$$

$$k_2 = \exp \left(\beta_3 - \beta_4 \left(\frac{523K}{T} - 1 \right) \right), \quad (30)$$

$$k_3 = \exp \left(\beta_5 - \beta_6 \left(\frac{523K}{T} - 1 \right) \right), \quad (31)$$

and

$$\Theta^\ominus = (1 + \beta_{11} \cdot p_{CO} + \beta_{12} \cdot p_{CH_3OH} + \beta_{14} \cdot p_{CO_2})^{-1}, \quad (32)$$

$$\Theta^\otimes = (1 + \beta_7 \cdot p_{H_2}^{0.5})^{-1}, \quad (33)$$

$$\Theta^* = \left(1 + \beta_9 \cdot p_{H_2O} + \beta_8 \cdot p_{CH_3OH} + \beta_{13} \cdot p_{CO_2} + \beta_9 \cdot \frac{\beta_{10}}{\beta_7^2} \cdot \frac{p_{H_2O}}{p_{H_2}} \right)^{-1} \quad (34)$$

ϕ is the catalyst state and is calculated using the following differential equation:

$$\frac{d\phi}{dt} = (k_1^+ y_{CO} + k_2^+ y_{H_2}) (0.9 - \phi) - \left(\frac{k_1^+}{K_1} y_{CO_2} + \frac{k_2^+}{K_2} y_{H_2O} \right) \phi \quad (35)$$

with

$$K_1 = \frac{k_1^+}{k_1^-} = \exp \left(\frac{-\Delta G_1}{RT} \right), \quad (36)$$

$$K_2 = \frac{k_2^+}{k_2^-} = \exp \left(\frac{-\Delta G_2}{RT} \right). \quad (37)$$

The reaction rate vector is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{r} = [r_{CO}, r_{CO_2}, r_{rwgs}] \quad (38)$$

The kinetic parameters are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameters for the kinetic model (Seidel et al., 2021) [6]

Parameter	Value	Unit
β_1	-5.001	-
β_2	26.455	-
β_3	-3.145	-
β_4	1.5308	-
β_5	-4.4526	-
β_6	-15.615	-
β_7	1.1064	bar ^{-1/2}
β_8	0	bar ⁻¹
β_9	0	-
β_{10}	0	bar ^{-5/2}
β_{11}	0.14969	bar ⁻¹
β_{12}	0	bar ⁻¹
β_{13}	0.062881	bar ⁻¹
β_{14}	0	bar ⁻¹
ΔG_1	0.3357×10^3	J/mol
ΔG_2	21.8414×10^3	J/mol
k_1^+	7.9174×10^{-3}	s ⁻¹
k_2^+	0.188×10^{-4}	s ⁻¹

2.2.2 Kortuz kinetics

Reaction rates [7]:

$$r_{\text{CO-Hyd}} = k_{\text{CO-Hyd}} p_{\text{CO}} p_{\text{H}_2} \Theta^{(s1)} \Theta^{(\text{shet})} \left[1 - K_{p,\text{CO-Hyd}}^{-1} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{CO}}^{-1} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-2} \right] \quad (39)$$

$$r_{\text{CO}_2\text{-Hyd}} = k_{\text{CO}_2\text{-Hyd}} p_{\text{CO}_2} p_{\text{H}_2} \Theta^{(s2)} \Theta^{(\text{shet})} \left[1 - K_{p,\text{CO}_2\text{-Hyd}}^{-1} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2} p_{\text{CO}_2}^{-1} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-3} \right] \quad (40)$$

$$r_{\text{wgs}} = k_{\text{wgs}} p_{\text{CO}} p_{\text{H}_2}^2 p_{\text{H}_2}^{-1} \left(\Theta^{(s1)} + \Theta^{(s2)} \right) \Theta^{(\text{shet})} \left[1 - K_{p,\text{wgs}}^{-1} p_{\text{CO}_2} p_{\text{H}_2} p_{\text{CO}}^{-1} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-1} \right] \quad (41)$$

$$r_{\text{autocat}} = k_{\text{autocat}} p_{\text{CO}_2} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{0.5} \Theta^{(s2)^2} \Theta^{(\text{shet})} \left[1 - K_{p,\text{CO}_2\text{-Hyd}}^{-1} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2} p_{\text{CO}}^{-1} p_{\text{CO}_2}^{-1} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-3} \right] \quad (42)$$

with

$$k_j = \exp \left(A_j - B_j \left(\frac{523\text{K}}{T} - 1 \right) \right) \quad (43)$$

$$j \in (\text{CO-Hyd}, \text{CO}_2\text{-Hyd}, \text{wgs}, \text{autocat})$$

and

$$\Theta^{(\text{shet})} = \left[1 + \beta_9 p_{\text{H}_2}^{0.5} + \beta_{10} p_{\text{H}_2} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} + \beta_{11} p_{\text{H}_2} \right]^{-1} \quad (44)$$

$$\Theta^{(s1)} = \left[1 + \beta_{12} p_{\text{CO}} + \beta_{13} p_{\text{CO}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{0.5} + \beta_{14} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-1} + \beta_{15} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} \right. \\ \left. + \beta_{16} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} + \beta_{17} p_{\text{CO}_2} + \beta_{18} p_{\text{CO}} p_{\text{H}_2} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} \right]^{-1} \quad (45)$$

$$\Theta^{(s2)} = \left[1 + \beta_{19} p_{\text{CO}_2} + \beta_{20} p_{\text{CO}_2} p_{\text{H}_2}^{0.5} + \beta_{21} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-2} \right. \\ \left. + \beta_{22} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-1.5} + \beta_{23} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-1} + \beta_{24} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} \right. \\ \left. + \beta_{25} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}} + \beta_{26} p_{\text{CO}} + \beta_{27} p_{\text{CO}} p_{\text{H}_2} p_{\text{H}_2}^{-0.5} + \beta_{28} p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}}^2 p_{\text{H}_2}^{-2} \right]^{-1} \quad (46)$$

The reaction rate vector is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{r} = [r_{\text{CO}}, r_{\text{CO}_2} + r_{\text{autocat}}, r_{\text{wgs}}] \quad (47)$$

It is important to note that, in contrast to all other kinetic models considered in this work, this model assumes the WGS reaction

instead of the RWGS reaction

The kinetic parameters are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Parameters for the kinetic model (Kortuz et al.,2025) [7]

Parameter	Unit	Value
$A_{\text{CO-Hyd}}$	β_1 [ln(mol s ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹ bar ^{<i>r</i>0})]	-10.671
$B_{\text{CO-Hyd}}$	β_2 [ln(mol s ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹ bar ^{<i>r</i>0})]	47.680
$A_{\text{CO}_2\text{-Hyd}}$	β_3 [ln(mol s ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹ bar ^{<i>r</i>0})]	-7.964
$B_{\text{CO}_2\text{-Hyd}}$	β_4 [ln(mol s ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹ bar ^{<i>r</i>0})]	31.468
A_{wgs}	β_5 [ln(mol s ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹ bar ^{<i>r</i>0})]	3.878
B_{wgs}	β_6 [ln(mol s ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹ bar ^{<i>r</i>0})]	26.586
A_{autocat}	β_7 [ln(mol s ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹ bar ^{<i>r</i>0})]	-3.107
B_{autocat}	β_8 [ln(mol s ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹ bar ^{<i>r</i>0})]	26.413
$\Theta^{(\text{shet})}$	β_9 [bar ^{-0.5}]	0
	β_{10} [bar ^{-0.5}]	0
	β_{11} [bar ⁻¹]	64.186
$\Theta^{(s1)}$	β_{12} [bar ⁻¹]	0
	β_{13} [bar ^{-1.5}]	0
	β_{14} [-]	53.379
	β_{15} [bar ^{-0.5}]	24.574
	β_{16} [bar ⁻¹]	0
	β_{17} [bar ⁻¹]	14.937
	β_{18} [bar ^{-1.5}]	0
$\Theta^{(s2)}$	β_{19} [bar ⁻¹]	0
	β_{20} [bar ^{-1.5}]	0.0359
	β_{21} [-]	0
	β_{22} [-]	0
	β_{23} [bar ⁻¹]	0
	β_{24} [bar ^{-0.5}]	0
	β_{25} [bar ⁻¹]	0
	β_{26} [bar ⁻¹]	0
	β_{27} [bar ^{-1.5}]	0
	β_{28} [-]	7.950

2.2.3 van Schagen kinetics

Reaction rates [8]:

$$r_{CO_2} = k_{CO_2} p_{CO_2} p_{H_2} \left(1 - \frac{p_{CH_3OH} p_{H_2O}}{K_{p,CO_2} p_{CO_2} p_{H_2}^3} \right) \Theta_{\ominus} \Theta_{\otimes} \quad (50)$$

$$r_{rwgs} = k_{rwgs} p_{CO_2} \sqrt{p_{H_2}} \left(1 - \frac{p_{CO} p_{H_2O}}{K_{p,rwgs} p_{CO_2} p_{H_2}} \right) \Theta_{\ominus} \Theta_{\otimes} \quad (51)$$

$$\Theta_{\ominus} = \left(1 + K_{oc} p_{CO_2} p_{H_2O} + K_{ox} \frac{p_{CO_2} p_{H_2O}}{p_{CO} p_{H_2}} \right)^{-1} \quad (52)$$

$$\Theta_{\otimes} = \left(\sqrt{p_{H_2}} + K_{\frac{CO}{\sqrt{H_2}}} p_{CO} \right)^{-1} \quad (53)$$

with

$$k_i = k_{0,i} \exp \left(\frac{-E_{a,i}}{RT} \right) \quad (54)$$

The reaction rate vector is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{r} = [0, r_{CO_2}, r_{rwgs}] \quad (55)$$

Kinetic parameter are found in Table 3.

Table 3: Parameters for the kinetic model (van Schagen et al.,2025) [8]

Parameter	Value
k_{0,CO_2}	4.779×10^{10}
E_{a,CO_2}	1.142×10^5
$k_{0,rwgs}$	3.529×10^{14}
$E_{a,rwgs}$	1.448×10^5
K_{oc}	3.052
K_{ox}	9.695×10^2
$K_{\frac{CO}{\sqrt{H_2}}}$	3.545×10^1

2.2.4 Nestler kinetics

Reaction rates [9]:

$$r_{CO_2} = \frac{k_1 \cdot K_2 \cdot p_{CO_2} \cdot p_{H_2}^{1.5} \cdot EQ_1}{(1 + K_1 \cdot p_{CO} + K_2 \cdot p_{CO_2}) \cdot (p_{H_2}^{0.5} + K_3 \cdot p_{H_2O})} \quad (56)$$

$$r_{rwgs} = \frac{k_2 \cdot K_2 \cdot p_{CO_2} \cdot p_{H_2} \cdot EQ_2}{(1 + K_1 \cdot p_{CO} + K_2 \cdot p_{CO_2}) \cdot (p_{H_2}^{0.5} + K_3 \cdot p_{H_2O})} \quad (57)$$

$$EQ_1 = 1 - \frac{p_{CH_3OH} \cdot p_{H_2O}}{p_{CO_2} \cdot p_{H_2}^3 \cdot K_{p,CO_2}} \quad (58)$$

$$EQ_2 = 1 - \frac{p_{CO} \cdot p_{H_2O}}{p_{CO_2} \cdot p_{H_2} \cdot K_{p,rwgs}} \quad (59)$$

Table 4: Parameters for the kinetic model (Nestler et al.,2020) [9]

Parameter	Unit	Value
k_1	$\text{mol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Pa}^{-1}$	$5.411 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-45,458}{R\cdot T}\right)$
k_2	$\text{mol}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Pa}^{-0.5}$	$24.701 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-54,970}{R\cdot T}\right)$
K_1	Pa^{-1}	$3.321 \cdot 10^{-18} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{109,959}{R\cdot T}\right)$
K_2	Pa^{-1}	$8.262 \cdot 10^{-6}$
K_3	$\text{Pa}^{-0.5}$	$6.430 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{119,570}{R\cdot T}\right)$

The reaction rate vector is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{r} = [0, r_{CO_2}, r_{rwgs}] \quad (60)$$

Kinetic parameter are found in Table 4. Note that the partial pressures for the Nestler kinetics are provided in pascal (Pa) instead of bar.

2.2.5 Vanden Bussche kinetics

Reaction rates [10]:

$$r_{CO_2} = \frac{k_1 \cdot p_{CO_2} \cdot p_{H_2} \cdot \left[1 - \frac{p_{H_2O} \cdot p_{CH_3OH}}{p_{H_2}^3 \cdot p_{CO_2} \cdot K_{p,CO_2}}\right]}{\left(1 + K_1 \cdot \frac{p_{H_2O}}{p_{H_2}} + K_2 \cdot p_{H_2}^{0.5} + K_3 \cdot p_{H_2O}\right)^3} \quad (61)$$

$$r_{rwgs} = \frac{k_2 \cdot p_{CO_2} \cdot \left[1 - \frac{p_{H_2O} \cdot p_{CO}}{p_{CO_2} \cdot p_{H_2} \cdot K_{p,rwgs}}\right]}{\left(1 + K_1 \cdot \frac{p_{H_2O}}{p_{H_2}} + K_2 \cdot p_{H_2}^{0.5} + K_3 \cdot p_{H_2O}\right)} \quad (62)$$

The reaction rate vector is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{r} = [0, r_{CO_2}, r_{rwgs}] \quad (63)$$

Kinetic parameters are found in Table 5.

Table 5: Parameters for the kinetic model (Vanden Bussche and Froment ,1996) [10]

Parameter	Unit	Kinetic parameters
k_1	$\text{mol}\cdot\text{kg}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{bar}^{-2}$	$1.07 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{36,696}{R\cdot T}\right)$
k_2	$\text{mol}\cdot\text{kg}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{bar}^{-1}$	$1.22 \cdot 10^{10} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-94,765}{R\cdot T}\right)$
K_1	–	3,453.38
K_2	$\text{bar}^{-0.5}$	$0.499 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{17,197}{R\cdot T}\right)$
K_3	bar^{-1}	$6.62 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{124,119}{R\cdot T}\right)$

3 Optimization

3.1 Reaction $A \rightarrow C$

The complete optimization problem for the forced periodic operation of the reaction $A \rightarrow C$ in a CSTR is formulated as follows:

$$\max_{\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}} \Phi_1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}) \quad (64)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}_{\text{in}}(t, \mathbf{u}), \dot{n}(t, \mathbf{u})), \quad t \in [0, \tau] \quad (65)$$

$$\mathbf{x}(0) = \mathbf{x}(\tau) \quad (66)$$

$$x_{\text{in},A}(t) = x_{\text{in},A,0}(1 + A_A \text{squ}(t)) \quad (67)$$

$$x_{\text{in},B}(t) = x_{\text{in},B,0}(1 - A_B \text{squ}(t)) \quad (68)$$

$$\dot{n}(t) = \dot{n}_{\text{in},0}(1 + A_n \text{squ}(t + \varphi)) \quad (69)$$

$$\frac{1}{\tau} \int_0^\tau \dot{n}_{\text{in}}(t) x_{\text{in},B}(t) dt = 0.5 \dot{n}_{\text{in},0} \quad (70)$$

$$x_{\text{in},A,0} + x_{\text{in},B,0} = 1 \quad (71)$$

$$A_A x_{\text{in},A,0} - A_B x_{\text{in},B,0} = 0 \quad (72)$$

$$\Phi_2(x, u) = \varepsilon \quad (73)$$

$$u_{\text{lb}} \leq u \leq u_{\text{ub}} \quad (74)$$

$$0 \leq x_c(t) \leq \bar{x}_c, \quad c = A, B, C \quad (75)$$

with

$$\Phi(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\tau} \int_0^\tau \dot{n}_{\text{in}}(t) x_C(t) dt, \\ \frac{\int_0^\tau \dot{n}_{\text{in}}(t) x_C(t) dt}{\int_0^\tau \dot{n}_{\text{in}}(t) x_{\text{in},A}(t) dt}, \end{cases} \quad (76)$$

The resulting input vector is defined as:

$$\mathbf{u} = [x_{\text{in},A,0}, x_{\text{in},B,0}, A_A, A_B, \tau, \varphi, \dot{n}_{\text{in},0}] \quad (77)$$

In the steady-state case, the amplitudes, period, and phase angle have no influence and are therefore omitted. The decision variable vector then reduces to:

$$\mathbf{u} = [x_{\text{in},A,0}, x_{\text{in},B,0}, \dot{n}_{\text{in},0}] \quad (78)$$

With Equation 19, which fixes the inert fraction to 50%, and Equation 20, which enforces the summation constraint, we have two equality constraints and three variables. This results in one degree of freedom. In this case, $x_{\text{in},A}$ and $x_{\text{in},B}$ are fixed at 50%, and only $\dot{n}_{\text{in},0}$ remains as a free optimization variable.

Equation (14) contains the differential equation derived from Equation 4,5, and 6. For the FBR, the problem formulation is identical, with the difference that the PDE from Equation 14,15, and 16 must be solved instead of an ODE. To solve the problem numerically, the differential equation is discretized using finite differences and transformed into algebraic equality constraints.

3.2 Methanol synthesis

The optimization problem for the forced periodic operation of methanol synthesis in a fixed bed reactor can be formulated as follows:

$$\max_{\mathbf{u}} \Phi_1(\mathbf{x}(t, \mathbf{u})) \quad (79)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{x}) \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dt} + \mathbf{W}(\mathbf{x}) \frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dz} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}) \quad (80)$$

$$\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (81)$$

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}) \leq 0 \quad (82)$$

$$\mathbf{lb}_{\mathbf{u}} \leq \mathbf{u} \leq \mathbf{ub}_{\mathbf{u}} \quad (83)$$

Equation 80 contains the partial differential equation that must be solved in this case. The initial and boundary conditions are incorporated into the constraint vector \mathbf{h} . To solve the problem numerically, both the temporal coordinate t and the spatial coordinate z are discretized and transformed into algebraic equality constraints.

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}_{\mathbf{k},\mathbf{l}}}{dt} = \frac{\mathbf{x}_{k+1,l} - \mathbf{x}_{k,l}}{t_{k+1} - t_k} \quad (84)$$

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}_{\mathbf{k},\mathbf{l}}}{dz} = \frac{\mathbf{x}_{k,l+1} - \mathbf{x}_{k,l}}{z_{l+1} - z_l} \quad (85)$$

This leads to the following optimization problem:

$$\max_{\mathbf{u}} \Phi_1(\mathbf{x}(t, \mathbf{u})) \quad (86)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \tilde{\mathbf{h}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (87)$$

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}) \leq 0 \quad (88)$$

$$\mathbf{lb}_{\mathbf{u}} \leq \mathbf{u} \leq \mathbf{ub}_{\mathbf{u}} \quad (89)$$

All constraints are described in Table 6.

Table 6: Constraints for forced periodic operation of methanol synthesis

		Mathematical formulation	Description			
$\tilde{\mathbf{h}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u})$		$\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{x}_{k,l}) \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_{k,l}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{W}(\mathbf{x}_{k,l}) \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}_{k,l}}{\partial z} - \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_{k,l})$	Discretized differential equation using orthogonal collocation			
		$\mathbf{x}_{1,l} - \mathbf{x}(\tau, z)$	Initial conditions			
		$\mathbf{x}_{k,l} - \mathbf{x}_0(t_k, u)$	Boundary conditions			
		$\epsilon - \Phi_2(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u})$	ϵ -constraint			
		$y_{in,CO_2,0} + y_{in,CO,0} + y_{in,H_2,0} + y_{in,N_2,0} - 1$	Summation condition for mole fractions			
		$A_{CO} y_{CO,0} + A_{N_2} y_{N_2,0}$	Ensures compensation of CO modulation with N ₂			
		$\frac{1}{\tau} \int_0^\tau \dot{n}_{in}(t) y_{in,N_2}(t) dt - \dot{n}_{in} y_{in,N_2}^{SS}$	Inert constraint			
$\mathbf{x}_0(t_k, \mathbf{u})$	y_{in,CH_3OH}	0	Boundary conditions specifying the inlet composition, inlet temperature, and inlet flowrate			
	y_{in,CO_2}	$y_{in,CO_2,0}$				
	$y_{in,CO}$	$y_{in,CO,0}(1 + A_{in,CO} \text{squ}(\omega t_k))$				
	y_{in,H_2}	$y_{in,H_2,0}$				
	y_{in,N_2}	$y_{in,N_2,0}(1 + A_{N_2} \text{squ}(\omega t_k))$				
	T	$T_{i,0}$				
	\dot{n}	$\dot{n}_0(1 + A_f \text{squ}(\omega t_k + \varphi))$				
$g(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u})$		$y_{in,CO,0} + y_{in,CO_2,0} - 0.01$	Minimum amount of reactants			
\mathbf{lb}_u	$y_{in,CO_2,0}$	0	\mathbf{ub}_u	$y_{in,CO_2,0}$	1	Bounds for inlet composition (ensuring hydrogen is in excess)
	$y_{in,CO,0}$	0		$y_{in,CO,0}$	1	
	$y_{in,N_2,0}$	0		$y_{in,N_2,0}$	1	
	$y_{in,H_2,0}$	0.35		$y_{in,H_2,0}$	1	
	A_f	0	A_f	1	Bounds for amplitudes	
	A_{CO}	0	A_{CO}	1		
	A_{N_2}	0	A_{N_2}	1		
	τ	36 s	τ	3600 s	Bounds for period	
	$\Delta\phi$	0π	φ	2π	Bounds for phase-shift	
	T_{in}	453.15 K	in	573.15 K	Bounds for inlet temperature	

4 Additional results

The following section presents additional results that support and reinforce the main findings of the manuscript.

4.1 Suboptimal solution with FPO for $\mathbf{A} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}$

The optimal FPO solution for the example reaction is characterized by a phase shift of $\frac{\pi}{2}$ between concentration and flow rate. This phase relationship gives rise to three distinct process phases: charging, batch, and discharging.

In the course of the optimization, a suboptimal solution was also identified. While this solution achieves a lower performance than the optimal case presented in the main manuscript, it still outperforms the steady-state operation on average. This suboptimal solution is illustrated in Figure 1. Here, the phase angle is around π (approximately 165°), which results in the two signals being nearly out of phase. As a consequence, only two distinct phases are observed. The behavior can still be interpreted based on a residence time effect: when the inlet concentration is high, the flow rate is low, and vice versa. However, the two input oscillations are not perfectly out of phase; a small offset remains. This offset causes the flow rate to increase shortly before

Figure 1: Temporal profiles of inlet and outlet variables for the reaction $A \rightarrow C$ in CSTR under suboptimal forced periodic operation.

the switching point, leading to a sharp release of product from the reactor. This explains the overshoots observed in the product flow rate during the transitions. A similar phase angle was also found in the experimental validation of liquid-phase reaction of acetic anhydride (157°) [11] and in the experimental validation of methanol synthesis (161°) [12].

4.2 Methanol synthesis

In the main manuscript, we focused exclusively on the isothermal case with constant temperature along the Pareto front. This was done to eliminate as many nonlinearities as possible from the process and to enable a clearer interpretation of "residence time effects".

For completeness, we also present here the more complex cases involving heat generation. These results demonstrate that the behavior of the isothermal reactor does not differ significantly from the non-isothermal cases, as the heat release is present but not as pronounced as in other highly exothermic reactions such as methanation [13]. Some of these aspects have already been discussed in [1].

4.2.1 Comparison: Isothermal and nonisothermal reactor with fixed temperature

To this end, we first compare the results between isothermal and non-isothermal CSTR and FBR configurations, where the reactor temperature (i.e., inlet and cooling temperature) is fixed at 503 K along the Pareto front. The corresponding results of optimal steady state and optimal FPO fronts are shown in Figure 2.

It can be observed that the Pareto fronts for both CSTR and FBR configurations exhibit similar shapes. However, the fronts corresponding to the non-isothermal case lie below those of the isothermal case, indicating that product yield is higher under isothermal conditions. Nevertheless, in both cases, forced periodic operation (FPO) leads to a clear performance improvement compared to steady-state operation. The figure also reveals that the optimal parameters differ slightly between the isothermal and non-isothermal reactors.

However, based on the steady-state Pareto fronts for the FBR, it can also be seen that the non-isothermal front partially lies above the isothermal one. This indicates that the fixed reactor temperature used in the isothermal case is not optimal under these conditions.

Figure 2: Comparison of forced periodic operation of methanol synthesis under isothermal and non-isothermal conditions with fixed reactor temperature (inlet/cooling).

4.2.2 Comparison: Isothermal and nonisothermal reactor with optimized temperature

Next, we consider the case in which the reactor temperature (i.e., inlet and cooling temperature) is constant over time but is optimized. The corresponding results are shown in Figure 3.

It can be seen that the isothermal and non-isothermal Pareto fronts are now nearly identical for both the CSTR and the fixed-bed reactor. Furthermore, the optimal parameter profiles along the fronts agree well, with the exception of the temperature. In the non-isothermal case, the optimized inlet and cooling temperatures are lower than in the isothermal case, which is physically reasonable. Due to the exothermic nature of the reaction, the reactor temperature rises internally, allowing the reaction heat to be utilized. As a result, although the inlet and cooling temperatures are lower in the non-isothermal case, the internal reactor temperature reaches a similar level as in the optimal isothermal case.

Figure 3: Comparison of forced periodic operation of methanol synthesis under isothermal and non-isothermal conditions with optimized reactor temperature (inlet/cooling).

4.2.3 Equilibrium

An interesting observation in the previous section is the inclusion of the equilibrium profiles. In the case of the fixed-bed reactor, the Pareto front for forced periodic operation (FPO) even lies above the steady-state equilibrium line. This observation can be explained by the fact that the equilibrium line is only intended as a rough reference. The equilibrium yield depends on pressure, temperature, and the inlet composition. However, for a given equilibrium yield, there is no corresponding product flow rate. To still illustrate the influence of the equilibrium, we chose to plot the equilibrium yield corresponding to each steady-state point (i.e., flow rate) along the Pareto front.

It should be noted that equilibrium depends on both temperature and composition, and in the case of FPO, the composition oscillates over time, and the temperature also differs from the steady-state case. Therefore, the steady state equilibrium line can be somewhat misleading when comparing it to the FPO front. Due to the oscillations in composition, the equilibrium also changes continuously throughout the cycle. This is illustrated in Figure 4. Here, we compare the FBR in four cases: isothermal and non-isothermal, each with fixed and optimized temperature. The red dotted lines represent the equilibrium yield corresponding to the FPO Front at each discretized time point, illustrating that the equilibrium also oscillates over time. In the case with optimized temperature, it can be seen that the equilibrium line corresponding to the steady-state front intersects the FPO front. However, due to the different composition and temperature in the FPO case, the equilibrium yield corresponding to FPO front oscillates and spans a range that lies significantly above the steady-state equilibrium and FPO front.

Figure 4: Comparison of equilibrium lines corresponding to the steady-state front and to the Forced periodic operation fronts under different operating conditions

4.2.4 Linear reaction rate

For completeness, we also show here not only the Pareto fronts based on the linearized reaction rate, but also the corresponding optimal operating parameters. Furthermore, the plots also include the steady-state points that were used to linearize the reaction rate. It is important to note that the steady-state Pareto front cannot simply be used for this purpose, as both the steady-state and FPO fronts are independently optimized, and the respective points do not correspond to each other. To determine appropriate steady-state points for the linearization, the average components inlet molar flow rates of the corresponding FPO points were calculated and used to simulate the respective steady-state conditions in order to obtain a steady state outlet composition. These steady-state points are also shown in the plot. Most of them lie on the optimal steady-state Pareto front, but at high yield values, some points fall below it. Therefore, the reference points used for linearization are not necessarily optimal, but rather suboptimal steady states.

Figure 5: Comparison of CSTR and FBR performance under FPO.

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